
ALEXANDR FEINBERG- THE BEST POET IN UZBEKISTAN AND RUSSIA

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Annotation: This article provides information about the life and creative work of the Russian poet and People's Poet of Uzbekistan Alexander Feinberg. Information about his works is provided.

Key words: Poet, poetry, Russian, Uzbek, author, journalism.

Annotatsiya: Бу мақолада рус шоири ва Ўзбекистон халқ шоири Александр Аркадьевич Файнбергнинг ҳаёти ва ижодий фаолияти ҳақида сўз боради. Унинг асарлари ҳақида маълумотлар тақдим қилинган.

Kalit so'zlar: Shoir, she'r, rossiyalik, o'zbek, yozuvchi, muallif, jurnalistika.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены сведения о жизни и творчестве русского поэта и народного поэта Узбекистана Александра Фейнберга. Приведена информация о его произведениях.

Ключевые слова: Поэт, поэзия, русский, узбекский, писатель, журналистика.

He was born on 2nd November in 1939 in Tashkent where his parents moved from Russia. The writer's father, Arkady Lvovich Feinberg (1891–1971), originally from Gatchina, graduated from the Institute of Technology and worked as a chief engineer at a distillery. Mother Anastasia Alexandrovna (1904–?), born in Moscow, worked as a machinist in a distillery. After completing seven years of school, Arkady entered the Tashkent Technical College of Topography. After graduating from college, he served in the military in Tajikistan. After graduating from Tashkent University in 1965, he studied part-time at the Journalism Department of the Faculty of Philology and worked in a student newspaper. In 1961, he married Inna Glebovna Koval. Alexander was a member of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan and the author of fifteen poetry collections (including a posthumously published two-volume work).

His poems were published in "Smena", "Yoshlik", "New world", "Asian Star", "New Volga" magazines and periodicals of foreign countries: USA, Canada, Israel. In Feinberg's poetry, past and present, West and East nationalism and internationalism are interconnected, creating a unique artistic world. Feinberg's lyrical hero is a person who has fully preserved his human essence in the age of historical and social series, is ready to extend a hand of compassion and help to others, and is suffering from unpleasant events and incidents happening on the globe. The best artistic experiences of Russian and European poets were shown in his poetic work. The traditions of Eastern classical poetry are not alien to his creative style. It is

said that A.Faynberg had a close relationship with such outstanding Uzbek poets as Abdulla Aripov, Erkin Vokhidov since he had spent his sizeable amount of time living and working in Tashkent. Moreover, his enthusiasm to poetry encouraged him to translate Alisher Navoi’s works into Russian.

The most remarkable of his accomplishments was the documentary movie scenarized after glorious “Pakhtakor-1979” football team. The film was named “Their stadium is in the sky” because of unexpected air catastrophe in 1979.

Futhermore, he was the member of Uzbek writers Union. In 2004, the first president of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov awarded him with “Deserved and accomplished poet of Uzbekistan” medal.

All things considered, final standpoint is that such poetry idols as Abdulla Aripov, Erkin Vokhidov and Aleksandr Faynberg are honored in nation’s hearts.

He died on October 14, 2009 in Tashkent. He was buried in the section of the Botkin cemetery in Tashkent.

The works of faynberg

«Старая песенка» ("Oldsong"), «Самаркандский базар» ("Samarkand bazaar"), «Картинка Самаркандского базара» ("Photo of Samarkand bazaar"), «Два грузина» ("Two Georgian"); about the city of Tashkent where he was born and raised: в "1943" ("1943"), «Незабудка» ("Don't forget me"), «С вокзала я...» "I am from the station...", «Трамвайный парк» ("Tram park"), «Взгляд из детства» ("One from childhoodlandscape"), «Город, который ты есть» ("The city where you are"), «5-ый проезд Жуковского» ("Zhukovsky's 5th lane"), «Город милый» ("Dear city"). A. Feynberg not only wrote poems, but also translated. He is our famous grandfather Alisher Navoi and one of the modern poets Abdullah Oripov, Erkin Vahidov, Askad Mukhtar, Gulchekhra Nurullaev translated his poems into Russian. His poems in 2004 Rustam Musurmanov translated into Uzbek.

At the end of the article I give an example from his poetry:

“Varaq”

Yulduzlarni asraydi falak,
Chuqur dengiz asrar durlarni.
Daftarimdan yirtilgan varaq,
Asragin men yozgan she'rlarni
She'r - nafaqat o'qimoq, uqmoq,
She'r yurakda yangragan tovush:
Qutqargandek taygada so'qmoq,
Tebrangandek ko'llarda qamish.

Avlodlarga kelmasin malol,
She'rlarim g'am chekmasin nochor,

Shamol, dengiz va yaproq misol

Nafas olsin, kulsin beg'ubor.

A PAGE

The sky protects the stars,

The sea holds mysteries.

A page torn from my notebook,

Poetry is not reading and learning

It is a sound in the heart.

As a path saves in the field,

As a cane sways in the lake.

Every line is my soul, every poem is my heart,

Forests birds and clouds are friends of their.

A page torn from my notepad,

Save my poems one by one.

Shouldn't be legwork for generations,

Shouldn't be sad my poems also.

Like the sea, wind and leave,

Let Breathe and smile purely.

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